

Applying Deep Reinforcement Learning for Complex Scheduling Problems in Shipbuilding: Insights and Challenges

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Abstract. This study develops and evaluates a deep reinforcement learning-based integrated scheduling framework for various shipyard scheduling problems. Compared to traditional heuristic and metaheuristic methods, DRL shows superior adaptability in complex environments, though conventional methods remain more efficient in some cases.

Keywords: Reinforcement learning, Deep learning, Scheduling, Shipbuilding

1 Introduction

Efficient scheduling with limited resources, alongside the procurement or development of new resources, constitutes a core competency for the manufacturing companies [1]. Resources of this context broadly encompass facilities, equipment, machinery, vehicles, and personnel necessary for operating manufacturing systems, transportation systems, logistics, and even for military organizations.

Optimized scheduling is particularly crucial in domains where resource utilization directly influences a performance of the organization, especially manufacturing ones [2], defense [3][4], logistics [5][6], and transportation [7][8]. These sectors typically face two significant challenges: maximizing effectiveness with given resources[9][10] and the demand for rapid decision-making in highly dynamic environments[11]. Consequently, developing real-time, optimized scheduling capabilities has become critical for addressing the complexities of modern industrial operations [1][12].

Shipbuilding represents a challenging domain due to its unique operational characteristics. Shipyards operate under highly constrained resource conditions, where resources such as overhead cranes, heavy transporters, and specialized equipment are not only limited but also significantly interdependent. Scheduling in shipyards have to manage complex, multi-stage processes involving steel cutting, block assembly, painting, outfitting and final assembly, each with complex precedence relationships and interdependencies. Moreover, shipbuilding environments are highly dynamic: schedules frequently change due to unexpected delays, fluctuations in material procurement and customer requirements.

Traditional scheduling approaches in shipyards typically rely on heuristic and metaheuristic methods, which often struggle to adapt to real-time changes and the dynamic nature of shipbuilding. These traditional methods are largely static, demanding substantial manual intervention to accommodate operational disruptions. Consequently, their effectiveness and scalability are significantly limited, leading to suboptimal resource utilization and frequent delays and even loss of cost.

Recently, reinforcement learning-based scheduling methods[13][14][15][16] have emerged as promising inductive alternatives, capable of real-time adaptive decision-making without explicit dynamic modeling. In particular, deep reinforcement learning (DRL) offers the advantage of learning complex interactions among multiple resource constraints and dynamically evolving processes, providing a data-driven and self-improving framework for scheduling optimization.

Despite notable progress in applying DRL to shipyard scheduling problems [16][17], existing studies often target specific, isolated scheduling scenarios. Such fragmented approaches diminish algorithm reusability and scalability, necessitating repeated developments for similar yet slightly varying problems.

Therefore, this study aims to introduce various shipbuilding scheduling problems addressed using deep reinforcement learning and systematically analyze their performance. The research highlights DRL's capability to

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effectively integrate structural and sequential scheduling characteristics into a comprehensive optimization framework, demonstrating its practical utility and adaptability in shipyard production planning compared to traditional planning methods.

2 Method

2.1 Deep reinforcement learning

DRL is a methodology that combines Reinforcement Learning (RL) with Deep Neural Networks (DNN) to solve decision-making problems in high-dimensional state spaces.

Traditional reinforcement learning methods were limited by the need to store value functions or policies in tabular form, making them impractical for large or continuous state and action spaces. By leveraging deep neural networks to approximate these functions, DRL enables learning and decision-making in complex, continuous environments. Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) algorithms can be broadly categorized based on whether they rely on an explicit model of the environment (Model-based RL) or not (Model-free RL). Figure 1 illustrates the hierarchical classification of DRL algorithms, organizing them into value-based and policy-based approaches under the model-free category, alongside the model-based category.

Figure 1. Hierarchical classification of Deep Reinforcement Learning algorithms based on learning strategy and methodology

Model-free RL methods learn optimal policies directly through interaction with the environment without constructing a predictive model of environment dynamics. They are further divided into two major types. First one is a value-based methods (Table 1), which learn value functions, such as Q-functions, to implicitly derive the optimal policy.

Table 1. Value based methods of reinforcement learning

Algorithm	Reference	Description
DQN	[18]	Learns a Q-value function using deep neural networks to approximate action values in discrete action spaces
Dueling DQN	[19]	Separates the estimation of the state-value function and the advantage function to improve learning efficiency

C51	[20]	Categorical distributional approach to model the distribution of returns instead of expected values
IQN	[21]	Generalizes distributional RL using implicit quantile networks to approximate value distributions flexibly

And second one is a Policy-based Methods(Table 2). These methods directly learn the policy function that maps states to actions, optimizing it through policy gradients.

Table 2. Policy based methods of reinforcement learning

Algorithm	Reference	Description
Policy Gradient	[22]	Directly optimizes the policy by computing gradients of expected rewards with respect to policy parameters
A3C	[23]	Asynchronous variant of actor-critic, running multiple agents in parallel for faster learning and exploration
PPO	[24]	Improves policy stability using clipped surrogate objective functions, widely used for robust performance
DDPG	[25]	Extends Q-learning to continuous action spaces using deterministic policies and target networks
TD3	[26]	Enhances DDPG by addressing overestimation bias and introducing delayed policy updates
SAC	[27]	Maximizes a trade-off between expected return and policy entropy for improved exploration and robustness

Model-based RL, in contrast, builds or utilizes an explicit model of the environment to simulate future outcomes and optimize policies accordingly. This approach is subdivided into two types depending on whether the model is externally given or learned during training.

In general, model-free methods, particularly PPO, have demonstrated strong empirical performance in industrial scheduling tasks due to their robustness and sample efficiency, motivating their selection for this study. However, this does not mean that model-free PPO is necessarily the best method for all scheduling problems. Depending on the type of problem, the best-performing algorithm should be selected through repeated experiments and comparative analysis with comparable existing methods.

2.2 Markov decision process

The Markov Decision Process is a mathematical framework that extends the concept of Markov chains by incorporating decisions and rewards. An MDP is a 5-tuple $(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{R}, \gamma)$ where each component plays a critical role in modeling the sequential decision-making process with a reinforcement learning(Table 3), where the state transition mechanism is shown at Figure 2.

Figure 2. State Transition in MDP

Table 3. MDP Components of scheduling problem

Component	Description
States (\mathcal{S})	Represents the configurations of the environment that the agent can observe. In scheduling of the manufacturing field, states typically encompass the status of resources (machines, workers, transporting facility), the progress of ongoing tasks, and the number of pending jobs. The state space may be discrete or continuous depending on the specific scheduling problem.
Actions (\mathcal{A})	Defines the set of possible decisions available to the agent at each state. In scheduling contexts, actions include assigning jobs to machines, prioritizing specific jobs, or determining resource assignment policy. The action space may vary based on the current state of the target system.
Transition Probabilities (\mathcal{P})	Describes the probability of transitioning from one state to another after taking a specific action. These probabilities capture the stochastic nature of the environment, where outcomes can be affected by various uncertainties such as equipment failures and variable working and waiting times.
Reward (\mathcal{R})	Assigns immediate numerical feedback to state-action pairs, quantifying the goodness of specific decisions. In scheduling of the manufacturing system, rewards are typically designed to give incentives to the on-time deliveries, the tardiness minimization, and optimize a load balancing.
Discount Factor (γ)	A value between 0 and 1 that balances the importance of immediate versus future rewards. A higher discount factor encourages long-term planning, which is crucial in shipyard scheduling where short-term optimizations might lead to downstream bottlenecks.

2.3 Environment modeling

To accurately represent the dynamic and stochastic characteristics of real-world scheduling environments, this study employs a Discrete Event Simulation (DES) model as the learning environment for reinforcement learning agents. In particular, a DES method allows modeling of complex manufacturing systems where state transitions are driven by discrete events, such as job arrivals, machine breakdowns, or job completions, rather than by continuous time progression.

Given the importance of integrating environmental stochasticity into the Markov Decision Process (MDP) formulation - specifically, the state transition probabilities \mathcal{P} - the DES model plays a crucial role in generating realistic transition dynamics. Instead of analytically predefining all possible state transitions and their probabilities (that is often impractical in large-scale, complex systems), the simulation dynamically determines state transitions based on the given rules, uncertainties, and the constraints (mainly coming from various type of resources) embedded in the DES model.

Figure 3. Internal structure of SimPy

In this study, to facilitate efficient development and flexible experimentation, the DES model is implemented using SimPy (Figure 3), a process-based discrete-event open source for Python. SimPy offers all the functions for

defining resources, processes, and event handling of the relevant manufacturing systems, thereby enabling the creation of simulation models.

By interacting with the SimPy-based DES environment, the deep reinforcement learning agent goes through a realistic experience of the scheduling problem, observes various state transitions, and receives returns in the form of rewards. This DES learning process not only enhances the agent's robustness to environmental variability but also ensures that learned scheduling policies are applicable to complex and real-world manufacturing systems.

3 Examples of the scheduling optimization with deep reinforcement learning

In this paper, practices for optimizing the scheduling of shipyard production processes using in-depth steel chemistry and discrete event simulation methods are introduced. The shipbuilding processes introduced in this paper are steel stock yard, quay assignment, multi-crane operation and block assembly lines, all of which require real-time dynamic scheduling in the yard.

3.1 Stacking problem of steel stock yard

In the practice of shipyard production scheduling, the steel stockyard presents a critical challenge due to the need to manage dynamically arriving steel plates while minimizing crane operations required for rearranging stock. Traditional heuristic and optimization methods struggle to cope with the vast solution space and arrival uncertainty inherent in real-world steel plate stacking problems.

Figure 4. Learning framework and MDP model for stacking problem

To address this, a deep reinforcement learning (DRL) approach was proposed based on the Asynchronous Advantage Actor-Critic (A3C) algorithm to optimize stacking policies in a stochastic steel stockyard environment[28]. The stacking problem was modeled as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), where the state encapsulates the current stacking configuration and the arrival pipeline, the action represents the selection of the stacking location, and the reward reflects the minimization of crane operations required for future retrievals. The learning framework is shown in Figure 4.

A simulation-based environment was constructed to replicate the arrival dynamics of steel plates, and state inputs were processed through convolutional neural networks to effectively capture the spatial characteristics of

the stockyard. The agent learned to stack steel plates adaptively based on fabrication schedules, even under conditions of random arrivals, by maximizing long-term cumulative rewards.

Figure 5. Performance validation with other methods (left: comparing with heuristics, right: comparing with genetic algorithm)

Results demonstrated that the DRL-based method significantly reduced crane operations compared to traditional genetic algorithms (GAs) and specialized heuristics. Notably, in large-scale scenarios, the proposed method achieved a 25% reduction in crane usage compared to initial random stacking and consistently outperformed GA in both solution quality and computational efficiency. While the DRL approach required more training time, once trained, it could make near-real-time stacking decisions, making it highly suitable for a dynamic shipyard environments. The comparison results with several heuristics and genetic algorithm are shown in Figure 5

This study highlights the effectiveness of deep reinforcement learning in handling stochastic, large-scale production planning problems and provides a foundational case demonstrating DRL's potential for a stacking problem.

3.2 Resource assignment problem of quay process

Efficient scheduling of quay wall resources has become increasingly critical in shipyards due to the rising demand for complex vessels such as LNG carriers, which require extensive post-outfitting work after launching. Given the limited availability of quay walls and the significant cost implications of delivery delays and vessel movements, optimizing quay wall allocation is a high-priority problem.

To address this challenge, the quay wall allocation problem modeled as a flexible job shop scheduling problem (FJSP) incorporating quay wall preferences and preemption conditions for post-outfitting processes[29]. Recognizing the complexity and large scale of the problem, they proposed a deep reinforcement learning (DRL) framework based on a graph neural network (GNN).

A novel heterogeneous graph method was introduced to efficiently represent the relationship between vessels and quay walls while reducing the computational burden compared to traditional disjunctive graph approaches. Each state was modeled as a graph, with vessel nodes and quay wall nodes connected by preference-ranked edges. Using this representation, a scheduling agent was trained within a Markov decision process (MDP) framework, where actions involved selecting vessel-quay wall assignments, and rewards reflected penalties for delivery delays, vessel movement costs, and processing cost variations.

The agent architecture combined heterogeneous graph transformers (HGT) to handle the diverse node and edge types, enabling it to learn rich contextual embeddings. Training was conducted via the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm, and a discrete-event simulation (DES) environment was developed to simulate the complex post-outfitting scheduling dynamics. The learning framework is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Learning framework and MDP model for quay assignment problem

Figure 7. Scalability test of quay scheduling problem

Experimental evaluations based on real-world shipyard data showed that the proposed approach significantly outperformed heuristic and metaheuristic methods (Figure 7). The DRL-based scheduling reduced overall post-outfitting costs by effectively balancing the trade-offs between minimizing vessel relocations, adhering to quay wall preferences, and avoiding costly delivery delays. Importantly, the agent demonstrated real-time decision-making capability after training, offering practical applicability to dynamic and large-scale shipyard operations.

This study exemplifies the potential of integrating deep reinforcement learning with graph-based modeling techniques to tackle complex scheduling problems in real industrial environments, providing further validation of DRL's relevance to smart shipyard production planning.

3.3 Multi-crane scheduling problem of overhead crane operation

Efficient scheduling of dual crane systems is important for optimizing operations in shipyard steel stockyards and even in most workshops with multiple overhead cranes, where cranes must manage complex material flows while avoiding route interference and ensuring timely deliveries. Traditional heuristic approaches face difficulties adapting to dynamic demands and handling multi-loading capabilities, limiting their applicability in real-world environments.

To address these challenges, a deep reinforcement learning (DRL) based scheduling algorithm designed for dynamic dual crane operations was tested in . The dual crane scheduling problem was formulated as a MDP, with state representations encoded as heterogeneous graphs capturing the relationships between cranes and steel plate

plates. By applying a Heterogeneous Graph Transformer (HGT) as the scheduling agent's core, the model efficiently extracted relational information (Figure 8, B) necessary to account for crane interference and pile stacking conditions (Figure 8, A).

Figure 8. Problem definition and heterogeneous graph representation of stockyard status

The action space involved selecting the next steel plate (or pile) to be moved, while a novel multiple-Loading heuristic was integrated to enable simultaneous transport of multiple plates within crane capacity constraints. A surrogate reward function, reflecting wasted time due to empty travel, crane interference avoidance, and idling, was designed to provide immediate feedback during training, focusing on minimizing the overall makespan.

Training was conducted using the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm in a discrete event simulation (DES) environment that dynamically modeled crane operations and collision avoidance behavior. After training, the DRL agent demonstrated real-time decision-making capabilities, significantly outperforming conventional heuristics and genetic programming (GP) heuristics across multiple experimental settings.

Figure 9. Scalability test of multi crane scheduling problem

Extensive experiments validated the proposed algorithm's effectiveness and generalization. The DRL-based approach consistently achieved shorter makespans, better balanced crane workloads, and showed robust scalability across different stockyard layouts and varying numbers of retrieval tasks. In particular, the DRL agent utilizing graph-based state encoding (RL-GNN) outperformed a vector-encoded DRL agent (RL-MLP) by approximately 7.5%, emphasizing the advantage of graph representations in capturing crane-task relationships (Figure 9).

This study highlights the potential of integrating deep reinforcement learning with graph neural networks and domain-specific heuristics to solve dynamic, large-scale scheduling problems in shipyard environments, offering a pathway toward autonomous, real-time production scheduling systems.

3.4 Permutation flowshop problem of block assembly line

The block assembly line in shipyards is a critical production stage where flat-shaped hull blocks are fabricated, typically forming bottlenecks due to the large volume and variability of work. Efficient sequencing of inbound blocks is essential to minimize the overall makespan and enhance shipyard productivity. Traditional heuristic and metaheuristic methods, such as dispatching rules and genetic algorithms, have been applied to this scheduling problem; however, they suffer from scalability issues and require complete re-optimization whenever the input settings change.

To overcome these limitations, a deep reinforcement learning approach proposed based on a pointer network architecture[30]. The block assembly line scheduling problem was formulated as a permutation flowshop scheduling problem (PFSP) without intermediate buffers, aiming to minimize the makespan across six consecutive workstations.

Figure 10. Summary of developed learning algorithm

Unlike conventional reinforcement learning algorithms that struggle with variable-sized input sequences, the pointer network flexibly handles different numbers of input blocks without retraining. The model was trained using a policy-gradient method, with Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) applied to stabilize learning. The state representation captured processing times of blocks at each station, and the output was a permutation indicating the processing order (Figure 10).

Training was conducted with synthetic datasets generated based on real shipyard data, where working times were fitted to log-normal distributions. Testing involved various block numbers (25, 50, 75, 100, 125) to evaluate the generalization capability. The trained model was compared against conventional heuristics (e.g., Palmer, Campbell, SPT, LPT) and metaheuristics (e.g., Simulated Annealing, Genetic Algorithm, NEH). The comparison results are shown in Table 4 and Table 5, each makespan and computing time respectively.

Table 4. Comparing with the other algorithms with makespan (hour)

Number of Jobs	Pointer network	Meta-heuristic			Heuristic				Random
		SA	GA	NEH	Palmer	Campbell	LPT	SPT	
25 EA	75.70	74.78	74.71	74.90	78.70	77.70	85.30	87.80	86.70
50 EA	138.50	138.09	138.14	137.90	142.90	141.60	152.90	157.30	152.90
75 EA	197.60	197.41	197.21	196.90	202.80	202.10	215.60	221.20	217.60
100 EA	264.60	264.81	264.51	264.00	271.60	270.00	283.60	292.60	284.30
125 EA	326.40	326.58	326.36	325.60	331.90	332.60	346.80	353.20	351.90

Table 5. Comparing with the other algorithms with computation time (sec.)

Number of Jobs	Pointer network	Meta-heuristic			Heuristic				Random
		SA	GA	NEH	Palmer	Campbell	LPT	SPT	
25 EA	0.50	4.48	1.52	0.10	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00
50 EA	0.80	8.59	3.21	0.60	0.00	0.30	0.00	0.00	0.00
75 EA	1.70	12.32	5.27	1.80	0.00	0.40	0.00	0.00	0.00
100 EA	2.70	16.32	7.63	4.00	0.00	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.00
125 EA	3.70	20.36	10.37	7.30	0.00	0.60	0.00	0.00	0.00

Results showed that the pointer network achieved near-optimal makespan performance, comparable to advanced metaheuristics such as NEH, while offering significantly faster computation once trained. Although NEH slightly outperformed the pointer network when the number of jobs was small, the pointer network demonstrated superior scalability as the number of blocks increased. Furthermore, unlike metaheuristics, which require fresh computation for each instance, the trained pointer network could generate solutions immediately, enabling real-time application in dynamic production environments.

This study highlights the feasibility and potential of using reinforcement learning-based pointer networks for complex, large-scale scheduling problems in shipbuilding, offering a scalable and efficient alternative to conventional optimization approaches.

4 Discussions

In Chapter 3, the applicability and effectiveness of Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) were validated through its application to various shipyard scheduling problems, which are characterized by high complexity and dynamic variability. Shipyard scheduling inherently involves intricate resource constraints, frequent schedule changes, and unpredictable environmental fluctuations. These characteristics expose the limitations of traditional optimization approaches such as heuristics and meta-heuristic methods, particularly in their ability to respond promptly to real-time changes. The DRL-based scheduling framework proposed in this paper showed a strong capacity to learn the complex, nonlinear relationships between system states and policies. It presented high adaptability to dynamic environments and superior generalization ability, enabling responsive and effective decision-making in real-time operational scenarios.

Figure 11. Learning framework and MDP model for activity scheduling

Figure 12. However, it is difficult to conclude that DRL methods are generally effective across all types of scheduling problems. In [31] of DRL-based activity scheduling optimization, the approach demonstrated its usefulness in improving existing plans through minor modifications. Learning framework for activity scheduling is shown at Figure 11, which is similar with the on of the stacking problem. In this study, the performance of the DRL was validated through the comparison with a manual method. As shown in Table 6.

As shown in Table 6, the proposed algorithm achieved improved load balancing in most test cases compared to the manually conducted activity scheduling. However, based on our internal experimental evaluations, the performance of the DRL approach was inferior to that of traditional optimization methods—such as Genetic Algorithms (GA), Simulated Annealing (SA), and constraint programming—when applied to full-scale activity scheduling optimization.

Table 6. Comparing with the other algorithms with workload deviation

Test number	Test case	Workload deviation			Improvement ratio w/ manual [(a)-(c)]/(a)	Improvement ratio w/ initial state [(b)-(c)]/(b)
		(a) Manual	(b) Initial	(c) DRL		
Test 1-1	Test 1	212.78	316.97	233.03	-10%	26%
Test 1-2				258.36	-21%	18%
Test 1-3				203.45	4%	36%
Test 2-1	Test 2	357.82	393.68	365.31	-2%	7%
Test 2-2				316.97	11%	19%
Test 2-3				313.23	12%	20%
Test 3-1	Test 3	185.16	172.94	147.45	20%	15%
Test 3-2				143.11	23%	17%
Test 3-3				134.71	27%	22%

5 Conclusion

This study explored the application of deep reinforcement learning (DRL) to complex scheduling challenges in shipbuilding, addressing problems such as steel stockyard stacking, quay wall allocation, multi-crane scheduling, and block assembly line optimization. Results demonstrated DRL’s superior adaptability and efficiency over traditional heuristic and metaheuristic methods, particularly in dynamic and unpredictable environments typical of shipbuilding processes. However, it was also observed that DRL does not universally outperform conventional optimization methods, highlighting the necessity of selecting appropriate algorithms based on specific problem characteristics. Future research should focus on developing multi-agent DRL systems, integrating hybrid optimization approaches, and employing transfer learning techniques to enhance generalizability and scalability, ultimately advancing DRL’s practical applicability in industrial shipyard scheduling.

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